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Companies and Universities Supporting the Act of Genocide in Gaza Through Financial Support or Public Statements: A Media Analysis

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Abstract

Following the Hamas attacks on Israel on October 7, 2023, multiple companies, individuals, and universities voiced their support for Israel, condemning the act of terrorism and extending humanitarian aid. This article analyzes the response of various entities, examining their public statements, donations, and support initiatives for Israel, especially in the context of the ongoing legal battle brought before the International Court of Justice (ICJ). *South Africa v. Israel*, a case filed on December 29, 2023, accuses Israel of violations under the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide due to its actions in Gaza during the Israel–Hamas war. The article explores the responses to these allegations and the broader political and ethical implications of support for Israel in a time of heightened scrutiny. Those voices mainly remained silent or provided further support for Israel against the convention of Genocide. This article raises concerns and awareness about the people and entities who are willingly complicit in the criminal acts against humanity.

Keywords: Israel, Genocide, Crime against humanity

Introduction

On October 7, 2023, Hamas launched a brutal and unprecedented attack on Israel, targeting civilians and military installations. The attacks have been widely condemned by numerous governments, international organizations, and institutions. However, the ensuing conflict, particularly the Israeli military response in Gaza, has led to a complex and controversial legal situation.

South Africa, on December 29, 2023, filed a case with the International Court of Justice (ICJ), accusing Israel of genocide in Gaza. The case highlights the broader debate over Israel's actions and the accusations of crimes against humanity. This legal proceeding, titled *South Africa v. Israel* (Document Number: 192-20240126-ORD-01-00-EN), pertains to the violations of the Genocide Convention, raising questions about Israel's military conduct and its impact on Palestinian civilians. As the case progresses, global support for Israel remains a topic of contention.

In this context, several companies, individuals, and universities have made their positions clear, either by condemning Hamas or by providing direct support to Israel. These entities, despite the ongoing ICJ case and the humanitarian crisis in Gaza, have expressed solidarity with Israel through statements, financial support, and organizational aid.

Corporate and Philanthropic Support for Israel

Major Companies Supporting Israel

In the aftermath of the Hamas attacks, several corporations made significant donations to Israel and related humanitarian efforts. These contributions not only reflect a commitment to humanitarian relief but also serve as a counter-narrative to the allegations surrounding the conflict. The following companies provided financial aid:

1. **Walmart:** Donated \$1M to the United States Holocaust Memorial Museum to support Holocaust education and anti-antisemitism initiatives (Walmart, 2023).

2. **Jefferies:** Committed \$8.6M to humanitarian aid, including a matching donation campaign with Bloomberg and other partners (Jefferies, 2023).
3. **Google & Alphabet:** Pledged \$8M to nonprofits, with \$3M dedicated to local emergency response efforts and \$3M to Gaza-related aid (Google, 2023).
4. **The Walt Disney Company:** Contributed \$2M to Magen David Adom and other Israeli organizations, coupled with employee matching gift programs (Disney, 2023).
5. **Salesforce:** Donated \$3M to various Israeli and humanitarian organizations, including \$1M each to United Hatzalah and Save the Children (Salesforce, 2023).

These companies, despite facing the backdrop of geopolitical tension and legal scrutiny, have reinforced their positions through philanthropy and public statements condemning violence against civilians, irrespective of the perpetrator.

Individuals Supporting Israel

Several prominent business leaders have been vocal in condemning the Hamas attacks and supporting Israel during the ongoing crisis. Their statements often emphasize the importance of upholding human rights and condemning terrorism, we could not find further evidence or retracement from their initial statements after they provided initial support for Israel, additionally many of them provided further fundamental means which has legalized Israel's genocidal acts in Gaza and the Lebanon:

- **Ed Bastian**, CEO of Delta Air Lines, condemned the attacks and supported U.S. repatriation efforts for affected citizens (Bastian, 2023).
- **Albert Bourla**, CEO of Pfizer, publicly denounced the violence and reiterated his commitment to healthcare and peace (Bourla, 2023).
- **Sundar Pichai**, CEO of Google, condemned the violence and pledged resources for relief efforts, expressing support for employees affected by the conflict (Pichai, 2023).
- **Jamie Dimon**, CEO of JPMorgan Chase, joined others in denouncing Hamas and reaffirmed his support for the safety of all individuals, especially those affected by terrorism (Dimon, 2023).

These leaders, many of whom manage global corporations, have utilized their platforms to advocate for peace and support humanitarian efforts, even amid the ongoing legal case that questions the actions of the Israeli government.

Academic Institutions and Their Responses

Universities Condemning Hamas and Supporting Israel

In addition to corporate and individual support, universities worldwide have played a role in shaping public discourse surrounding the Israel–Hamas conflict. Many academic institutions have issued statements condemning the actions of Hamas and expressing solidarity with Israel, though the legal and ethical complexities of the conflict are often acknowledged.

1. **Harvard University:** President Claudine Gay condemned the Hamas attacks, distancing the university from student organizations that supported the violence (Harvard University, 2023).
2. **University of California (UC):** Regent Richard Sures condemned Hamas, calling for the university to retract any supportive statements made by its student groups (UC Regents, 2023).
3. **University of Oxford:** The leadership issued a statement condemning the Hamas attacks and reiterated its stance against antisemitism and violence (University of Oxford, 2023).
4. **Duke University:** President Price condemned the attacks and extended support to the university community affected by the violence (Duke University, 2023).
5. **University of Wuerzburg:** University leadership expressed solidarity with Israel and condemned the attacks, reaffirming the institution's commitment to peace (University of Wuerzburg, 2023).

However, the university sector has also faced controversy. In some cases, criticism has arisen regarding delayed or insufficient condemnations, especially from student bodies or faculty members with more sympathetic views towards Palestinian causes. These internal debates reflect broader societal divisions, with some questioning the Israeli government's actions in Gaza.

Legal Challenges and International Scrutiny

The ongoing case at the International Court of Justice (*South Africa v. Israel*) raises significant questions about international law, state sovereignty, and the prevention of genocide. South Africa's application to the ICJ calls for Israel to cease actions it believes are genocidal and violating the Genocide Convention. This case is particularly pertinent as the court deliberates on Israel's conduct during the Gaza conflict, which has led to widespread casualties and a deteriorating humanitarian situation.

Despite these legal proceedings, many entities, both private and public, have continued to support Israel. Their support is often framed as a moral stance against terrorism, in favor of the preservation of life and security for civilians in Israel. At the same time, these entities maintain their humanitarian efforts, recognizing the need for assistance to Palestinian civilians affected by the ongoing violence.

Conclusion

As the International case against *Israel* continues to unfold at the International Court of Justice, the global response to the Israel–Hammas conflict remains deeply divided. Companies, individuals, and universities that have supported Israel are doing so amid a complex legal and moral landscape, balancing their commitments to humanitarian aid, corporate responsibility, and the protection of human rights.

In an era where public opinion is increasingly shaped by international law, media coverage, and corporate interests, these entities must navigate the difficult terrain between supporting Israel's and addressing the broader humanitarian concerns raised by the ongoing conflict. As the ICJ case progresses, it is clear that the international community will continue to debate the legal and ethical dimensions of the Israel–Hammas war, with implications for both international diplomacy and corporate responsibility.

Acknowledgement: Dr. Amirali R. Davoudpour is an associate professor at the Iranian Canon of Medicine and Law, a non-governmental organization dedicated to protecting the civil rights of Iranian and Afghan migrants.

Annex

Companies Supporting Israel

Company	Donation / Support Details
Walmart	\$1M donation to the United States Holocaust Memorial Museum for Holocaust education and anti-antisemitism programs.
Jefferies	\$8.6M to humanitarian aid; \$4.4M additional donation, matching funds from Bloomberg and others.
Google & Alphabet	\$8M committed to nonprofits; \$3M for local emergency response and \$3M for Gaza aid.
Verizon	\$1.5M donation to relief organizations; matching employee donations up to \$1,000; waiving international charges.
The Walt Disney Company	\$2M donation to Magen David Adom and other nonprofits; employee matching gifts program.
American Express	\$1.5M donation; \$750K to Magen David Adom, matching employee contributions.
Salesforce	\$3M initial donation; \$1M each to United Hatzalah, Save the Children, Holocaust Survivors' Association.
Boeing	\$2M emergency assistance; donations to Magen David Adom, NATAL, Red Cross, and vulnerable populations.
GE	\$500K donation to American Red Cross for regional relief; matching employee donations.
Mercedes-Benz	€1M donation to United Hatzalah and German Red Cross for humanitarian aid.
Accenture	\$3M donation; \$1.5M each to Magen David Adom and Palestinian Red Crescent; matching employee donations.
Citigroup	\$1M donation to humanitarian organizations in Israel through Citi Foundation.
Oracle	\$1M donation to Magen David Adom; employee fundraising campaign.
Goldman Sachs	\$2M donation; matching employee donations 3-to-1.
Mattel	Donations of cash and toys to shelters and hospitals in Israel for children.
Insight Partners	\$1M donation to humanitarian aid work.

Company	Donation / Support Details
General Catalyst	\$250K pledge to humanitarian efforts.
Fox Corporation	\$1M donation to United Jewish Appeal.

Individuals Supporting Israel

Person	Role / Company	Support Details
Ed Bastian	CEO, Delta Air Lines	Condemnation of attacks, cancellation of TLV flights, support for U.S. repatriation efforts.
Sasan Goodarzi	CEO, Intuit	Support for employee safety in Israel, donation to humanitarian relief efforts.
Albert Bourla	CEO, Pfizer	Condemnation of attacks, commitment to healthcare, support for global peace efforts.
Jonas Prising	CEO, ManpowerGroup	Condemnation of attacks, support for impacted colleagues in Israel.
Eran Feigenbaum	SVP & Country Leader, Oracle Israel	\$1M donation to Magen David Adom; internal fundraising campaign to support Israel.
Sundar Pichai	CEO, Google & Alphabet	\$8M to nonprofits, support for employees affected, and a balanced approach to the crisis.
Jane Fraser	CEO, Citigroup	Emotional support for colleagues in Israel, financial aid for humanitarian efforts.
Pablo Di Si	CEO, Volkswagen	Support for Israel, monitoring situation, checking on impacted employees.
Bob Iger	CEO, The Walt Disney Company	Condemnation of attacks, support for Jewish employees, focus on education and empathy.
Sergio Ermotti	CEO, UBS	\$10M pledged for emergency relief, condemnation of terrorism, fundraising appeal for affected areas.
Jamie Dimon	CEO, JPMorgan Chase	Condemnation of attacks, support for employees and the people of Israel.
David Solomon	CEO, Goldman Sachs	Support for employees, condemnation of terrorism, focus on humanitarian aid.
Satya Nadella	CEO, Microsoft	Condemnation of attacks, focus on employee safety, financial support for humanitarian relief.

Person	Role / Company	Support Details
Kathleen Hogan	HR Chief, Microsoft	HR programs to support impacted employees, connecting with local organizations for assistance.
Tim Ryan	Chairman, PwC	Initial \$250K donation to Red Cross, focus on emergency relief efforts for both Israeli and Palestinian needs.
Mike Bloomberg	Founder, Bloomberg LP	Matched \$2M donation for Magen David Adom (through Jefferies).
Mark & Erica Gerson	Philanthropists	Matched \$2M donation to United Hatzalah (through Jefferies).
Kathleen Hogan	HR Chief, Microsoft	Support for relief efforts through company programs.

University	Person	Details
University of Oxford	University leadership	Condemned the Hamas attacks and reiterated its commitment to opposing antisemitism and terrorism.
Harvard University	President Claudine Gay	Forcefully condemned the Hamas attack on Israel and distanced the university from student organizations supporting the attack.
University of California (UC)	Regent Richard Sures	Called on UC to retract supportive statements about Hamas and condemned the Hamas attack unequivocally.
Stanford University	Various alumni	Alumni criticized the university's delayed response and lack of clear condemnation of Hamas' attack.
Catholic Colleges & Universities	No specific person named	Several Catholic colleges condemned the Hamas attack on Israel, including leaders from the Association of Catholic Colleges and Universities.
Tufts University	No specific person named	Denounced the praise of Hamas by some student groups and condemned the attack.
Cornell University	Multiple professors, university leadership	Condemned the Hamas attacks after initial controversy and clashes over earlier statements.
Ruhr University Bochum	Chancellor and leadership	Condemned the Hamas attacks, highlighting the atrocities committed by Hamas and expressing solidarity with Israel.
University of Maryland	President Darryll Pines	Condemned the Hamas attacks, emphasizing the need for peace and support for those affected by the violence.

University	Person	Details
University of Southwestern Ontario	University leadership	Strongly condemned the terrorist attack on Israeli civilians and reaffirmed the university's stance against violence.
Aberdeen University	Sanaa al-Azawi (PhD student)	Proposed a motion condemning Israel's actions towards Palestinians but faced calls for clearer condemnation of Hamas' attacks.
Yale University	President Peter Salovey	Condemned the Hamas attack as terrorism, distanced the university from groups supporting the attacks, and reaffirmed support for Israel.
Duke University	President Price	Condemned the Hamas attacks in Israel, calling them terrorist actions and offering support to the university community impacted by the violence.
Brandeis University	President Ron Liebowitz	Condemned the Hamas attacks on October 7, expressing strong disapproval of terrorism and violence.
University of Pennsylvania	President Liz Magill	Condemned Hamas's terrorist assault on Israel, particularly the violence against civilians, and expressed solidarity with the victims.
Tulane University	University leadership	Condemned Hamas's attacks on Israeli civilians, calling them horrific and expressing grief and support for those affected.
New York University (NYU)	President Andrew Hamilton	Condemned the deadly terrorist attacks by Hamas on Israel and expressed the university's stance against such violence.
York University	University leadership	Condemned statements by student unions that referred to the Hamas attack as a "strong act of resistance," clarifying support for the victims of the violence in Israel.
University of Wuerzburg	University leadership	Strongly condemned the Hamas attacks, reaffirming its commitment to peace, security, and support for Israel.